

ULTRALIGHT GRAPHENE COMPOSITE SANDWICH FOR STRETCHABLE LIGHT-EMITTING DISPLAY

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ABSTRACT

Graphene composite sandwiches with exceptional stretchability and electrical conductivities are fabricated using porous graphene honeycomb (GH)/polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) composites as the core material and ultrahigh-density graphene foam (UDGF)/PDMS composites as the face sheets. The microscale GHs prepared by a 3D printing technique deliver a long-range ordered hexagonal porous structure, an excellent electrical conductivity as high as 72 S/m, along with an ultralow density of 3.25 mg/cm³. To the best of authors' knowledge, this is the lightest honeycomb structure ever reported in open literature. Taking advantage of the engineered porous structure of GHs, the graphene composite sandwich shows minimal resistance changes at large external deformations with excellent structural durability. A stretchable light-emitting display constructed using a graphene composite sandwich is demonstrated as the electric circuit, which delivers reliable electronic performance under different loading modes.

1 INTRODUCTION

Stretchable electronics have attracted a great deal of attention due to their potential applications in emerging devices, such as stretchable displays and bio-integrated devices [1,2]. One of the biggest challenges in the development of stretchable electronics is the fabrication of stretchable conductors, which are capable of simultaneously achieving excellent electronic performance and mechanical robustness. A potential solution is to prepare composites consisting of conductive fillers dispersed in an elastomer matrix. However, their performance is unsatisfactory due to the unstable conductive networks and the significantly reduced stretchability at high filler contents. Use of three dimensional (3D), interconnected conductive networks to replace the dispersed fillers can be an ideal, alternative approach. There has emerged a variety of 3D conductive networks with porous structures, including foams, sponges and aerogels constructed by metal nanowires [3], CNTs [4,5] and graphene [6–8]. However, achieving a long-range ordered and precisely controlled porous structure remains challenging. Recently, a 3D printing technique has gained tremendous attention due to its capability to rapidly produce 3D objects by a layer-by-layer deposition method directly from digital computer aided design (CAD) files [9], making it a perfect candidate to fabricate 3D conductive networks with tailored porosities and precisely controlled structures.

In this study, we report the fabrication of microscale graphene honeycombs (GHs) with a long-range ordered porous structure by 3D printing technique. The GH/poly (dimethylsiloxane) (PDMS) composite was combined with ultrahigh-density graphene foam (UDGF)/PDMS composite face sheets to assemble graphene composite sandwiches that delivered a tiny resistance change in response to large external strains. A stretchable light-emitting display was demonstrated using the graphene composite sandwich as the electric circuit, which exhibited reliable electronic performance under different loading modes, including stretching and bending.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Fabrication of GH and graphene composite sandwich

Graphene oxide (GO) dispersions with concentrations ranging from 0.5 to 4 mg/mL were prepared based on the modified Hummers method using natural graphite flakes (supplied by Asbury Graphite Mills) [10,11]. The graphene composite sandwich consisted of a GH/PDMS composite core and two UDGF/PDMS composite face sheets. Figure 1 presents the fabrication procedure of graphene composite sandwiches. Briefly, an acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS) template with honeycomb pillar arrays were 3D-printed. The mixture of GO dispersion and L-ascorbic acid at a weight ratio of 1:10 was then infiltrated into the template, followed by heating at 60 °C for 1 h for mild gelation. After washing with DI water for 24 h and subsequent freeze drying for 48 h, a graphene aerogel (GA) was removed from the ABS template, which was reduced at 900 °C for 2 h to obtain GH. The as-prepared GH was immersed into a PDMS/ethyl acetate solvent mixture at a weight ratio of 1:5, followed by heating at 80 °C for 2 h for simultaneous evaporation of the solvent and curing to obtain porous GH/PDMS composites. As for the face sheets, UDGF was fabricated by template-based chemical vapor deposition using a compressed Ni foam template, following our previous study [8]. The freestanding UDGF was infiltrated with a PDMS/curing agent mixture under vacuum, and the two films were assembled with a core and co-cured at 60 °C for 2 h to obtain the graphene composite sandwich.

Figure 1: Fabrication procedure of graphene honeycomb (GH) and graphene composite sandwich.

2.2 Characterization

A scanning electron microscope (SEM, JEOL 6390F) was used to characterize the morphologies of GH and porous GH/PDMS composites using secondary electron beams at an acceleration voltage of 20 kV. The surface chemistry of GHs were examined by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), and the degree of reduction of GHs were evaluated using Raman spectroscopy. A CHI660c electrochemical workstation was utilized to measure the electrical conductivities of GHs and graphene composite sandwiches based on a two-probe method. Mechanical tests of graphene composite

sandwiches under cyclic tensile and bending loads were conducted on a universal testing machine (MTS Alliance RT/5) at a cross-head speed of 1 mm/min. A data logger (34970A Data Acquisition/Data Logger Switch Unit, Agilent) was used to monitor the resistance change of graphene composite sandwiches under different loading modes at 2 Hz [12].

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Morphologies of GHs and porous GH/PDMS composites

Figure 2 presents typical morphologies of GHs and porous GH/PDMS composites. It is seen that the freestanding GH before infiltration of PDMS had a hierarchical porous structure, consisting of porous GA walls with a pore size of $\sim 10 \mu\text{m}$ and long-range ordered hexagonal large pores with an edge length of $\sim 800 \mu\text{m}$, as shown in Figures 2a and c. The GH/PDMS composite after the infiltration of PDMS preserved the original porous structure of GH, Figures 2b and d. The hierarchical porous structure with hollow hexagonal large pores similar to the freestanding GHs were maintained due to the only partially-infiltrated thin coating of PDMS.

Figure 2: Optical images (a,b) and SEM images (c,d) of GH and porous GH/PDMS composites, respectively.

3.2 Properties of GHs and porous GH/PDMS composites

The XPS and Raman spectra were utilized to characterize the chemical attributes of GO and GH, as shown in Figures 3a and b. The XPS C 1s deconvoluted spectra (Figure 3a) indicate that most oxygenated functional groups, including carboxyl, epoxy, and carbonyl groups, were eliminated after thermal reduction at 900 °C, resulting in a surged C/O atomic ratio from 2.2 for GO to 38 for the GH. The effectiveness of reduction was further confirmed by the Raman results (Figure 3b): the D- to G-band peak intensity ratio, I_D/I_G , decreased from 2.5 to 1.7 after thermal reduction, resulting from the removal of oxygenated functional groups from GO sheets. The efficient reduction gave rise to excellent electrical conductivities of the resulting GHs as high as 72 S/m at an ultralow density of 3.2 mg/cm³, as shown in Figure 3c. To the best of authors' knowledge, this is the lightest honeycomb structure ever achieved in open literature with such a high electrical conductivity. Both the electrical

conductivity and density increased with increasing GO concentration thanks to the formation of increasingly denser conductive networks.

The normalized resistance changes of ordinary GA/PDMS composites without hexagonal pores and porous GH/PDMS composites are shown in Figure 4a. The GA/PDMS composite was prepared by partially infiltrating PDMS into GA, similar to the fabrication procedure of the porous GH/PDMS composites. The resistance of GA/PDMS composites drastically increased by more than 1200% after stretching 60%, whereas an almost negligible resistance change of less than 60% was shown by the porous GH/PDMS composites at the same strain. Obviously, the ordered hexagonal large pores in GH/PDMS composites played an important role in the reduction of resistance change. To understand the underlying mechanism, Figure 3b presents the shape changes of the large pores during stretching from 0 to 60%. It can be seen that the structure of the composite remained intact after stretching while the GH cellular walls were stretched along the loading direction along with elongated pores. Such elongation of large pores effectively reduced the strains felt by the conductive walls, leading to a very low resistance change of porous GH/PDMS composites.

Figure 3: (a) XPS C 1s deconvoluted spectra and (b) Raman spectra of GO and GH; (c) electrical conductivities and densities of GH as a function of GO concentration.

Figure 4: (a) Resistance changes of GA/PDMS composites without hexagonal pores, and porous GH/PDMS composite as a function of tensile strain up to 60%; (b) Optical images of a porous GH/PDMS composite at different tensile strains from 0 to 60%.

3.3 Performances of graphene composite sandwich and the stretchable light-emitting display

The porous GH/PDMS composites were then combined with thin UDFG/PDMS composite face sheets to construct graphene composite sandwiches. The face sheets played dual functions of transferring strains uniformly to the inner porous GH/PDMS composite core and effectively connecting the conductive path of the porous core in the in-plane direction. Figure 5a shows the stress-strain curves of the graphene composite sandwich under cyclic stretching at different maximum tensile strains from 20% to 60%. The sandwich was able to stretch up to 60% and return to the original shape upon unloading for over 100 cycles, reflecting its stable structure. In addition, the sandwich delivered excellent durability as shown in Figure 5b. Because the external strain was effectively shared by the long-range ordered pores of GH/PDMS composite core, a very low and repeatable resistance change of $\sim 60\%$ was obtained at a 60% tensile strain. Apart from stretching, the sandwich also presents stable electrical performance upon bending. The electrical resistance slightly increased with decreasing bending radius, and presented a small resistance change of only $\sim 2.6\%$ at a small bending radius of 3.0 mm, a testament to the composite sandwich structure without apparent permanent damage caused by bending cycles, see Figure 5c.

Taking full advantage of exceptional capabilities of graphene composite sandwiches in terms of stretchability, electrical conductivity and durability, a stretchable light-emitting display was prepared using the composite sandwich as electric circuit, as shown in Figure 6a. 5×5 LED arrays were fixed on a thin PDMS insulating layer of $\sim 500 \mu\text{m}$ in thickness, which were connected to the patterned composite sandwich circuit according to the circuit diagram in Figure 6b. The display was then connected to a microcontroller, capable of switching on and off of each LED pixel depending on the program compiled. In the current study, the main function of the display was to show scrolling text according to the input information. The display was able to present stable performance under different loading modes, such as stretching and bending, as shown in Figures 6c and d.

Figure 5: (a) Stress-strain curves of graphene composite sandwich at tensile strains of 20%, 40%, and 60%; Normalized resistance changes of sandwich (b) for 100 cycles at 0 to 60% tensile strain, and (c) upon bending for ten cycles each at different maximum bending radius, ρ .

Figure 6: (a) Schematic of stretchable light-emitting display constructed using graphene composite sandwich; (b) Circuit connection in the stretchable display electronic system; and photographs of the stretchable display (c) in bending and (d) stretching.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In summary, we fabricated an ultralight graphene composite sandwich consisting of a porous GH/PDMS composite core made by 3D printing and UDFG/PDMS composite face sheets. The resultant sandwich was highly stretchable, durable and electrically conductive, which delivered very a low resistance change under different loading modes, such as stretching, bending and twisting. The exceptional performance of sandwich arose from the long range ordered porous structure of GH, capable of effectively sharing the external strains. The practical application of the composite sandwich as stretchable displays was demonstrated by connecting 5×5 LED arrays to the patterned sandwich circuit. The highly flexible display possessed extremely stable electronic performance under different loading modes.

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